

The Effects of Foreign Direct Investment on Growth in the Cemac¹

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Abstract

This paper analyses the effects of FDI on CEMAC's economic growth. Using a model that takes into account the interdependence of macroeconomic variables representing the channels through which FDI influences growth (human capital, technology transfer and import of capital goods, infrastructure, export, employment, per capita income, exports) to identify the direct and indirect explanatory mechanisms by which FDI acts positively or negatively on the CEMAC economy. The model estimate is based on CEMAC statistical data collected from 1976 to 2020. The CEMAC entity seems to have benefited from the benefits of FDI inflows and has various fortunes in the region's various countries.

Keywords

FDI, Economic Growth, A Model with a System of Simultaneous Equations, CEMAC..

1. Introduction

The effects of FDI are variously appreciated in the CEMAC area. While many agree that they are one of the main drivers of development because of the liquidity they bring to a hitherto low-performing area, Others argue that NMFs constitute a dual economy and even create a phenomenon of crowding out local firms.

The benefits of FDI are not automatic and are not distributed equally between countries and economic sectors. For FDI to have maximum positive effects, it is the responsibility of host countries to create favorable investment conditions and build the human and institutional capacity to exploit them.

Measures taken in 1999 following the implementation of the Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAP) aimed to make the CEMAC economy more competitive and credible in the eyes of potential investors.

The economic opening that followed these measures and the discoveries of oil deposits, in Equatorial Guinea and Chad in particular, had the effect of increasing FDI inflows into the area. Since then, there has been significant economic growth, with a rate of nearly 6% since 1995.

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Is this upsurge in growth linked to FDI inflows? In general, through what channels are the effects of FDI on growth in this sub-region manifested?

This paper attempts to answer these questions. In Section 2, we review the literature on the different effects of FDI in the host countries. Particular emphasis is placed on developing countries whose situation is similar to that of CEMAC countries to isolate the factors and mechanisms to be studied. In particular, this section reviews analyses of the impact of FDI on host countries in terms of employment, income, technology transfer, human capital, domestic investment, and foreign trade. We then present in Section 3 a structural model with simultaneous equations linking these different variables, applied to each of the CEMAC countries and the area taken as an economic entity. The model is estimated by the triple least squares method. Section 4 presents the mechanisms and effects of FDI obtained from econometric results. And section 5 concludes.

2. Literature review

Numerous empirical studies have analyzed the impact of FDI on developing countries with divergent results. While some studies argue that FDI has positive effects on the economic growth of host countries, others believe that FDI is not a necessary or sufficient condition. In the literature on the effects of FDI in the host countries, two main streams of analysis are generally distinguished: a causal study between FDI and growth (first paragraph), a study of the impact of FDI on host countries in terms of employment, income, technology transfer, human capital, domestic investment, and foreign trade (second paragraph).

2.1. FDI-growth causality analyses

Several studies have attempted a causal analysis between FDI and growth with divergent results.

A study published by the World Bank in 1999 to find a relationship between FDI and the growth of developing countries shows that FDI flows increase total investment and hence the growth of developing countries.

Borensztein (1998) used an endogenous growth model, goes in the same direction: FDI facilitates technology transfer, raises the skill level of workers, and tends to increase exports and competitiveness in developing countries. Their panel study of 69 developing countries shows that a one percentage point increase in the FDI-to-GDP ratio increases the host country's GDP per capita growth rate by 0.8 percent.

For Wacziarg (1998) each percentage point of the FDI-to-GDP ratio is associated with an increase in the growth rate of GDP per capita from 0.3 to 0.4 percent. These results are identical to those of Blomstrom, Lipsey, and Zejan (1992), whose study focuses on high-income developing countries. Loesse (2005) in the search for a relationship between FDI and economic growth in Côte d'Ivoire finds that between 1970-2001, foreign direct investment was an important source for growth. All other things being equal, one percentage point of additional FDI entering Côte d'Ivoire leads to an increase in GDP per capita growth of 0.01 percent. The author argues that the investment incentive policies implemented have helped to increase FDI flows and thus the productive capacity of the economy, increasing gross domestic product.

However, a study on the effects of FDI in 73 developing countries by Singh (1988) does not show any significant effect.

An econometric study conducted by Nair-Reichert and Weinhold (2001) using the Holtz-Eakin causal test on a panel of 24 developing countries between 1971 and 1995 found no causal relationship between FDI and growth.

In the same vein and using a neoclassical production function, Saltz (1992) finds a negative correlation between FDI and economic growth. According to him, FDI increases the overall level of investment, and improves productivity in some cases, but in many others tends to reduce the rate of growth. To confirm its conclusions, the author studies the FDI-growth relationship in a sample of countries divided into two distinct groups, depending on whether they receive more or less FDI. The author finds that in developing countries that accept the repatriation of profits without any constraint, FDI has no positive effect on growth. In particular, the author argues that if FDI results in capital raising in the host country market, it results in a redistribution of labour-intensive industries to capital-intensive industries, creating a net loss of employment and subsequently a decline in consumer demand. Another negative effect may result from the excessive extraction of minerals or the over-specialization of production on a particular good that would result in lower export prices and a deterioration in the terms of trade of the host country.

Similarly, Carkovic and Levine (2002) find no link between FDI and growth in a sample of World Bank countries.

Similarly, Chowdhury and Mavrotas (2003) find that "FDI does not cause growth" in the sense of Granger in Chile, while this causal relationship is bidirectional in the case of Malaysia and Thailand.

Other studies in the search for a link between FDI and growth have given ambiguous results, including a large study conducted by UNCTAD (1999). To avoid frequently encountered correlation problems, the authors used panel data and lagging variables over a set of 100 countries over five years. Of all the explanatory variables used, only the variables representing the level of education were significant.

In this vein, Zhang (2001) investigates the relationship between FDI and growth in 11 countries in Asia and Latin America. It uses country-specific time series and conducts long-term causal tests based on the error correction model. The results show that there is no relationship between FDI and growth in Argentina in the short and long term while there is indeed a relationship of growth towards FDI in Brazil in the short term and the long term in Colombia. For Asian countries, the author finds a short-term relationship of growth towards FDI in Korea, Malaysia, and Thailand. In 5 of the 11 countries studied, growth is accelerated by FDI. For six countries, there is no co-integration relationship between FDI and growth; only one country shows a causal relationship between growth and FDI.

De Melo (1999) attempts to correct the econometric deficiencies raised in early studies by doing both a time series test and a panel data test. It does this by selecting a sample of OECD and non-OECD countries. In the first case, De Melo begins his Granger causality test with a stationarity test and then checks the short- and long-term relationships between the two variables with a usual test (cointegration), and finally finishes his analysis with a panel data test. De Melo argues that while FDI can foster economic growth, this relationship depends on the degree of complementarity and substitution between FDI and domestic investment.

2.2. The impact of FDI in host countries

The impact of FDI in the host countries has been extensively documented. The studies place particular emphasis on the effects of FDI on employment and poverty reduction, the transfer of technologies and the formation of human capital capable of controlling them, the evolution of domestic investment, exports and foreign trade.

2.2.1. Effects on employment

There are two contrasting trends in the spillover effects of FDI on employment in the host countries, some praising their merits, others denouncing them (Root and Ahmed (1979), Schneider and Frey (1985) and Hanson (1996)).

With regard to the first trend, an empirical contribution of the effects of FDI on employment is made by the model of Mickiewicz, Radocevic and Varblane (2000).

Hunya and Geishecker (2005) in researching the effects of FDI on employment in Eastern European countries after decentralisation, Note that the job losses resulting from the privatisation of state-owned enterprises have led to the restructuring of these enterprises, which are proving to be more efficient and effective.

2.2.2. Effects on income distribution

Some authors argue that these effects are positive in the distribution and improvement of workers' incomes, others do not.

The positive effects of FDI have been verified in the field of income and wealth redistribution in some developing countries such as Botswana unlike other countries such as Zaire (de Mobutu) and Angola (de Dos Santos) where money from multinationals was used either to bribe politicians or to buy weapons (Mold (2004)).

According to Klein, Aaron and Hadjimichael (2001), FDI has a direct effect on poverty reduction.

In conclusion, we can say with Lipsey (2002) that it is necessary to take into account the specificities and policies of countries as well as the characteristics of firms and industries to assess the impact of FDI on incomes and poverty.

2.2.3. Effects on technology transfer

In a major review of the literature in this field, De Mello (1997) shows two main ways in which FDI encourages growth. The IDEs allow the diffusion of technical progress through training effects and knowledge transfer, in particular through the acquisition of new managerial and organisational techniques.

Nelson and Phelps (1966), Jovanovic and Rob (1989), Grossman and Helman (1991), Segerstrom (1991) and Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1995), using an endogenous growth model, argue that FDI helps to promote growth in developing countries by facilitating technology transfer, increasing the skill level of workers and, above all, increasing exports and competitiveness. For them, FDI plays a central role in the development process.

Similarly, the results of the work of Barrell and Pain (1996) and Borensztein et al. (1998) and the work of Brooks and Hill (2004) suggest that technology transfer is a channel through which growth can be promoted.

For Engelbrecht (1996), research and development activities carried out by foreign multinational firms exert a contagion effect on local firms, both in terms of manpower training and in terms of input yield.

2.2.4. Effects on human capital

Studies on the role of FDI in driving economic growth through improved human capital were conducted by Markusen (1995). These authors argue that a technological change introduced by multinational firms can cause imitation and training effects in the industrial sector.

In summary, it can be estimated with Blomström and Kokko (2003) that countries with relatively high levels of human capital have the capacity to attract technology-intensive foreign investment, which can help to increase the qualification of local work. On the other hand, in countries where the initial conditions are less favourable, the multinationals investing there will tend to use simpler technologies which will contribute marginally to the learning and development of a local qualification. Research on the relationship between FDI and human capital formation still needs to be deepened and raises the question of public policies to be implemented to improve the absorption capacity of host countries.

2.2.5. Effects on domestic investment

In empirical studies on the effects of FDI, a central question regularly comes back to the extent to which FDI exerts a crowding or a ripple effect on domestic investment. This issue has been widely addressed by Borenstein. Other theoretical studies also consider that there are possible complementarity effects between FDI and domestic enterprises (Rodriguez-Clare, 1996; Markusen and Venables, 1999).

Bosworth and Collins (2000) estimate the effects of FDI and capital flows on domestic investment for a panel of 58 developing countries between 1978 and 1995.

Similarly, Agosin and Mayer (2000) study the impact of FDI on domestic investment by region, using a smaller sample than that of Bosworth and Collins (32 countries) but a longer period (1970-1996).

It should however be noted that despite the «crowding in» effect FMN, the eviction effect has often been observed at the level of developing countries and the question is whether we can talk about eviction effect in a region like CEMAC where there are not really local companies capable of compete with NMFs.

It seems more realistic to assume that the impact of FDI on domestic investment is dynamic in nature and can occur in two stages:

- i. a negative initial effect due to the entry of the multinational which, because of its competitive advantages, gains market share to the detriment of local companies;
- ii. a more favourable long-term effect on local businesses, which benefit from the externalities associated with the activities of multinationals, through a «demonstration effect» or the dissemination of know-how.

2.2.6. Effects on exports and foreign trade

Dunning (1998) was one of the first economists to speak of a direct link between FDI and economic policy through trade. FDI can make a significant contribution in foreign currencies to developing countries. Dunning explains this phenomenon by the simultaneous presence of three advantages for FMN: «ownership-specific advantage», 2) «location advantage», and 3) «internationalization advantage», that is to say the specific advantages related to the property, Localization and Internationalization of Commerce (OLI).

Aitken et al (1997) show that the presence of multinational firms in the domestic market not only stimulates competition but also encourages domestic firms to export and improve their efficiency.

3. Econometric model

The econometric model developed to analyze the effects of FDI in CEMAC is a model with a system of simultaneous equations. It is intended to take into account the interdependence between the selected variables.

It should be remembered that a model with a system of simultaneous equations can be solved in two ways. Either solve the equations of the system one by one in the form of multiple regressions, or solve them simultaneously. In both cases, it is necessary to respect an elementary rule: the number of endogenous variables must be equal to the number of equations. The second method is preferred to the first despite its complexity, because having the advantage of being clear about the choice of instruments used. The equations of the dynamic interdependent model we use are estimated by the least squares triples (TMC).

The choice of a dynamic model of the least squares triples is the appropriate method when the explanatory variables are correlated with the error terms and when there is a heteroscedasticity.

We present successively: i) the system of equation tested, ii) the definitions of the variables used in the econometric analysis, iii) the statistical data, sources and techniques of data collection, iv) the estimation method.

3.1. The model: a system of simultaneous equations

In order to take into account the econometric deficiencies previously mentioned in the literature review, we intend to build a structural model composed of several simultaneous equations. The aim here is to link economic growth to FDI and other factors such as exports, human capital, employment, infrastructure, etc. The general form of the system can be written as follows:

$$f(y_t, x_t, \beta) = \varepsilon_t$$

Where y_t is the vector of endogenous variables, x_t the vector of exogenous variables and ε_t is the vector of residues possibly correlated; the purpose of the estimate is to find the vector of parameters β .

The structure of the model is represented by a system of eight simultaneous equations as follows:

Equation n°1:

$$\ln(EXP_{it}) = f(\ln EXP(-1), \ln IMP_{it}, GR_{it}, \ln FDI_{it}, \ln INV_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln IC_{it}, \ln HC_{it}, \ln IFR_{it}, \ln TCH_{it})$$

Equation n° 2:

$$\ln(IMP_{it}) = f(\ln IMP(-1), GR_{it}, \ln FDI_{it}, \ln EXP_{it}, \ln HC_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln IC_{it}, \ln INV_{it}, \ln IFR_{it})$$

Equation n° 3:

$$\ln EMP_{it} = f(\ln EMP(-1), \ln IMP_{it}, \ln EXP_{it}, \ln IC_{it}, \ln IFR_{it}, \ln FDI_{it}, GR, \ln HC_{it}, \ln INV_{it})$$

Equation n° 4:

$$\ln HC_{it} = f(\ln HC(-1), GR, \ln FDI_{it}, \ln INV_{it}, \ln IMP_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln EXP_{it}, \ln IC_{it})$$

Equation n° 5:

$$\ln IC_{it} = f(\ln IC(-1), \ln IMP_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln IFR_{it}, \ln FDI_{it}, GR, \ln HC_{it}, \ln INV_{it})$$

Equation n° 6:

$$\ln(INV_{it}) = f(\ln INV(-1), \ln FDI_{it}, GR, \ln HC_{it}, \ln IMP_{it}, \ln IFR_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln EXP_{it}, \ln IC_{it}, \ln TINF_{it})$$

Equation n° 7:

$$\ln IFR_{it} = f(\ln IFR(-1), \ln FDI_{it}, \ln HC_{it}, GR, \ln INV_{it}, \ln IMP_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln IC_{it}, \ln EXP_{it})$$

Equation n° 8:

$$GR = f(\ln IFR_{it}, \ln HC_{it}, \ln INV_{it}, \ln IMP_{it}, \ln EMP_{it}, \ln IC_{it}, \ln EXP_{it})$$

with:

GR_{it}: annual growth rate of the country's GDP i.

Ln is set for logarithm

HC_{it}: human capital available in country i at time t.

FDI_{it}: FDI flows entering country i at time t.

IMP_{it}: import of physical capital goods from country i at time t.

EMP_{it}: total employment available in the country at time t.

IC_{it}: income per capita in CEMAC countries

IFR_{it}: infrastructure available in country i at time t

EXP_{it}: exports from country i to time t

INV_{it}: domestic investment in country i at time t.

i = 1..... i represents each of the CEMAC countries

t = 1976..... t = 2020: time index.

β₀: constant term.

This model consists of eight endogenous variables (stated to the left of the equal sign of each of the eight equations above) and twelve exogenous variables, eight delayed endogenous variables of a period and four purely exogenous iso-temporal variables: (inflation rate (INF), interest rates (INT), exchange rates (EXR) and FDI.

3.2. The variables

3.2.1. Endogenous variables

Exports: Ln (EXP)

This is the total exports of goods and services at constant prices of each CEMAC country. Export revenues have always been the main resource of developing countries in general and in particular those of Central Africa. They allowed these countries to build up reserves, with the help of which they ensured

the repayment of their external debts and the settlement of their import bills. From this perspective, their instability has been detrimental to the growth of these economies. It has prevented an adequate, stable and sustainable development policy. With regard to equation (1), as we have seen in the previous section, the direct and indirect impact of FDI on exports has been the subject of a wide literature with sometimes mixed results. We test whether there is a positive sign between FDI and exports in CEMAC countries and in the area in general.

Imports of capital goods: Ln (IMP)

This variable is the sum of imports of capital goods other than the agricultural sector: machinery and spare parts, turnkey factories and industrial equipment, the purchase of patents and goods used in the drilling and exploitation of oil wells. IMP is used as a proxy variable for the possible diffusion of technologies incorporated in machinery and other industrial goods according to the importance of the absorption capacities and innovation efforts of the host country. We test whether there is a positive sign between FDI and capital goods imports in equation (2).

Employment: Ln (EMP)

This is the number of active persons in the period 1976-2020. At the CEMAC level, this variable will be the sum of each of the five CEMAC countries. In equation 3 we test whether there is a positive effect of FDI on employment.

Human capital: Ln (HC)

Countries with a critical mass of skilled human resources have grown rapidly. We take as a proxy variable for human capital in CEMAC the number of people enrolled in the 15-24 age group, as in most studies where data are difficult to collect. The variable is reported between 1976 and 2020 in all CEMAC countries. We check in equation 4 whether there is a possible positive effect of FDI on human capital.

Per capita income: Ln (CI)

The national income per capita is equal to the total national income divided by the number of inhabitants. Unlike per capita GDP, it integrates the income of nationals living abroad and removes that of foreigners living on the national territory (including the repatriation of profits from NMFs). Taking national income is very important in African countries because of many migrant workers who live abroad and ship their assets to their home country. The IC can be chosen in addition to the GDP growth rate because of the lack of correlation between these two variables. The purpose of the test here is to determine whether FDI directly and/or indirectly promotes the increase in national income per capita (Equation 5) and whether this has an effect on growth (Equation 8).

Domestic investment: Ln (INV)

Domestic investment is the total investment expressed in dollars deflated by the basic price index 100 in 1990 in the CEMAC between 1976 and 2020. In particular, we test in equation 6 whether there is a crowding in effect or a crowding out effect between inward FDI flows and domestic investments.

Infrastructure: LnIFR

Infrastructure is generally made up of communications routes (paved and unpaved roads, maritime communications routes, number of hospital beds per capita, telephone lines per country, etc.). For lack of statistical data, we take for proxy of the infrastructures the number of telephone lines. The estimation of equation 7 seeks to see if there is a positive effect of FDI on infrastructure development as is often the case in the literature.

The growth rate: GR

The variable considered here is the annual rate of change (expressed as %) in GDP (at constant prices) of the economy. Equation (8) seeks to capture the growth effects of the previous 7 variables, which may be influenced by FDI.

3.2.2. Exogenous variables

The exogenous variables are: exchange rate, interest rate and price growth rate and FDI. Delayed endogenous variables of a period are also considered in this model as explanatory. Moreover, and this is the interest of the model, an endogenous variable is often considered as an explanatory variable in another equation.

Regarding instrumental variables, the choice is very delicate and as envisaged in most econometric textbooks (Greene, Maddala and Wu), exogenous variables (delayed or not) and delayed endogenous variables are retained as instruments. Each equation of the system will have as instruments its endogenous variable delayed by two periods and the exogenous variables not delayed or/and delayed by one period.

3.3. Statistical data

We use data from 1976 to 2020 for the five Central African countries of Cameroon, Gabon, Congo, Equatorial Guinea and Chad. It is clear that in CEMAC as in all developing countries, the lack of statistical data is the main limitation encountered by researchers and this study is no exception to the rule. The data comes from a variety of sources, the most important of which are: the Université de Sherbrooke website (part of the growth and FDI data), the University of Toronto website (consumption, export, import), the Bank of Central African States (part of the GDP growth rate data, and some macroeconomic data), the national administrations of the five CEMAC countries, the United Nations Statistics Division, the Franc Zone Institute, the Banque de France website, and Eurostat.

When an observation is missing between two values, we use the interpolation method. When there are many missing values, we assign them the average of the last 10 years, if not the last five years.

Similarly, in order to make the series stationary, we use the logarithmic functions of all series. However, since the model is in logarithmic form, the problem of negative observations or null values must be addressed.

The exchange rate used in this work is the official rate between the euro/dollar and the CFA franc, ie one euro/dollar for 650/580 CFA francs. It should be remembered that there is a fixed parity between the euro and the CFA franc, while this parity does not exist between the dollar and the CFA franc.

3.4. Statistical Estimation Method

We use before any estimation the Dickey-Fuller Augmented (1981) test to test the unit root and we use the appropriate information criteria (Akaike (AIC) and Schwarz(SIC) information criteria), etc.) in order to determine the structures of the delays necessary for the series under study.

Blough (1992) argued that unit root tests can falsely reject the null non stationarity hypothesis when growth or FDI has weak power against the alternative hypothesis. This is due to the fact that in finite samples, it has been discovered that some unit root processes exhibit a behavior close to a stationary white noise process.

These methodological problems are in fact due to the use of critical values based on the asymptotic Dickey-Fuller distribution. Thus, given all these potential problems in the unit root test, we use the results of the KPSS test described in Kwiatkowski et al. (1992) to confirm the validity of the results of the Dickey-Fuller Augmented test. This test actually lets us know if the ADF test is valid.

After carrying out the preliminary tests, we then proceeded to estimate the models themselves. It should be noted here that for a dynamic model, the Durbin Watson (DW) test is not valid, which is why we opted for the neutralization of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in the model using the robust version of the triples least squares model.

Basically, the preliminary tests demonstrate the evidence of a good econometric specification of the model. Similarly, the stability of the variables GR and Ln (FDI) could be verified. Indeed, all the roots are within the unitary circle and meet the conditions of stability in all countries taken individually and in the CEMAC area taken as an entity. The model was estimated using the Ordinary Least Squares Triple (TMCO) method for the reasons discussed above.

3.5. Estimation procedure

The estimation of our model will be done in two stages: the estimation of equations one to seven and the estimation of equation eight.

First, the effects of FDI on the various variables that can influence economic growth are assessed: the effects of FDI on exports (eq.1), capital goods imports (eq.2), employment (eq.3), human capital (eq.4), per capita income (eq.5), domestic investment (eq.6) and infrastructure (eq.7).

The second step measures the impact of these variables (EXP, IMP, HC, IC, INV, IFR) on growth. This step is based on the estimation of equation 8, without the IDE as an explanatory variable, from the system of equations with eight equations and eight endogenous variables.

We conclude this section with a synthetic analysis of the effects of FDI on CEMAC growth as derived from the different model results.

4. Results

4.1. Indirect effects of FDI on CEMAC growth

In view of the results obtained, all variables are stationary in level, first difference or second difference and valid at different conventional levels (1%, 5% and 10%) in all CEMAC countries, as well as in CEMAC taken as an entity. ADF test results are presented in Table 1 for CEMAC. We present the results of the effects of FDI on the different channels through which they pass to influence growth

(indirect effects) before considering the effects of FDI on growth per se in CEMAC and finally the mechanisms of FDI transmission on growth.

Table 1 : Unit Root Test Result

CEMAC Zone				
Variables	ADF	ADF Probability	Order integrative	Decision of the stationarity
IFR	-4.805848	0.0019(***)	I(1)	Yes
FDI	-7.996747	0.0000(***)	I(1)	Yes
EXP	-2.816504	0.0645(**)	I(2)	Yes
IMP	-2.817013	0.0060(***)	I(2)	Yes
IC	-6.543735	0.0039(***)	I(1)	Yes
INV	-3.941062	0.00039(***)	I(1)	Yes
EMP	-5.544151	0.0000(***)	I(1)	Yes
GR	-2.719049	0.0080(***)	I(2)	Yes
HC	-4.052273	0.0139(**)	I(0)	Yes

NB: (***) The probabilities of the ADF test are significant at the 1% threshold

(**) ADF test probabilities are significant at 5% threshold

4.1.1. Effects of FDI on exports (Ln (FTE), eq.1)

The model presented in Table 2 has a 56% coefficient of determination with an adjusted coefficient of determination of 44%. The coefficient of determination is quite low, but as we know, it's less important in this kind of model. Basically, it appears that the effect of FDI on exports is positive and significant. This finding supports many empirical studies that support the hypothesis of the positive contribution of NMFs to the host country's export performance. The result of the CEMAC is explained by the nature of the exported products: natural resources and in particular hydrocarbons and generally because the FMN subsidiaries established in CEMAC adopt a vertical strategy by exporting part of their production to their countries of origin or to their parent firms.

There is a non-significant relationship between export and exchange rate in this area, which reinforces the idea that monetary variables rarely play a key role in macroeconomic policy in the franc area of which CEMAC is a part. Indeed, and in general, a policy of currency devaluation serves to make more competitive the products of the country that devalues, and thus tends to increase its exports. The exchange rate plays only a marginal role here because of the fixed monetary parity of the franc zone with the euro, except in case of devaluation which happens very rarely. It must be said that products exported by CEMAC countries (particularly hydrocarbons) are always in demand regardless of the exchange rate.

It can also be noted that Chad and Congo have had a surplus trade balance in value in recent years thanks to FDI from the oil sector. Equatorial Guinea is the first country to host FDI in CEMAC and thanks to oil exports, huge trade surpluses that make it the holder of more than half of CEMAC's financial

reserves in the Bank of Central African States (BEAC). The non-significant effect of FDI in this country is due to the fact that oil revenues date only from the early 2000s.

Table 2: CEMAC Export Equation Estimate

Dependent variable:EXP				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	-7.366	6.986	-1.054	0.292
EXP(-1)	0.389	0.236	1.641(*)	0.098
FDI	0.218	0.107	2.1693(**)	0.005
GR	0.062	0.127	0.492	0.622
IC	-0.008	0.103	-0.084	0.932
INV	0.159	0.169	0.938	0.348
HC	-0.001	0.003	-0.538	0.590
IFR	0.002	0.017	0.13	0.896
EXR	1.426	1.208	1.18	0.238
EMP	-0.024	0.152	-0.162	0.871
R squared	0.569	Mean dependent var		6.853
Adjusted R squared	0.440	S.D.dependent var		0.290
S.E. of regression	0.046	Sum squared resid		0.070
Durbin Waston stat	1.945			

Student test in parenthesis: (**) significant at 5%. P-value: relative to the test performed.

4.1.2. The effects of FDI on the import of capital goods (Ln (IMP), eq. 2)

The estimate of equation 2 is given in Table 3. The coefficient of determination is 88% and the adjusted coefficient of determination is 86%. FDI is significant and positive (the Student test is significant at 1%), which means that a change in FDI leads to a change in capital goods imports in the same direction at the CEMAC level. This is in line with the results obtained by Nelson and Phelps (1966), Jovanovic and Rob (1989), Grossman and Helman (1991), Segerstrom (1991) and Barro and Sala-i- Martin (1995) and Borensztein (1998) in the context of the developing countries. It is also explained by the tax advantages that host countries grant to NMFs, which encourages them to import more material used in the processing or production of goods for export. It is also noted that an increase in per capita national income (GNI) increases imports of capital goods (MPI).

Table 3: Estimation of the import equation for capital goods

Dependent variable:IMP				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	2.722	1.650	1.65	0.100
IMP(-1)	0.286	0.383	0.745	0.456

FDI	0.231	0.117	1.972(**)	0.048
GR	0.218	0.193	1.126	0.260
IC	0.216	0.132	1.971(**)	0.049
INV	0.115	0.225	0.512	0.609
HC	0.008	0.013	0.627	0.530
IFR	0.001	0.002	0.592	0.554
EXR	-0.017	0.282	-0.063	0.949
R squared	0.889	Mean dependent var		6.978
Adjusted R squared	0.862	S.D.dependent var		0.253
S.E. of regression	0.093	Sum squared resid		0.290
Durbin Waston stat	1.622			

Student test in parenthesis: (**) significant at 5%. P-value: relative to the test performed.

4.1.3. Effects of FDI on employment (LnEMP, eq.3)

The results of the model presenting the effects of FDI on employment are given in Table 4. The adjusted coefficient of determination is 99%. FDI is significant (at the 10% threshold) with a positive sign. An increase in FDI inflows tends to lead to an increase in employment in the CEMAC. Thus, there is no “crowding out” effect between employment and FDI inflows into CEMAC.

We also see that per capita income is significant and affects employment. In other words, the more income a country has, the more it has the ability to create jobs.

All CEMAC countries therefore benefit greatly from FDI for job creation. The State also needs the revenues generated by the oil royalties resulting from the FDI invested to create public and parapublic jobs.

Table 4: Estimation of the employment equation

Dependent variable:EMP				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	0.026	0.136	0.191	0.848
EMP(-1)	0.766	0.234	3.274(***)	0.001
EMP(-2)	0.226	0.227	0.995	0.320
FDI	0.001	0.001	1.437(*)	0.151
GR	0.008	0.002	0.402	0.687
IC	0.004	0.001	2.387(**)	0.017
INV	-0.002	0.003	-0.681	0.496
HC	-9.190	0.0001	-0.640	0.522
IFR	2.150	4.460	0.480	0.630
EXR	0.006	0.008	0.720	0.472
R squared	0.98	Mean dependent var		6.788

Adjusted R squared	0.97	S.D.dependent var	0.109
S.E. of regression	0.0007	Sum squared resid	1.872
Durbin Waston stat	1.82		

Student test in parenthesis: (***) significant at 1%, (*) significant at 10%.

P-value: relative to the test performed. Robust test to autocorrelation.

4.1.4. Effects of FDI on human capital (LnHC, eq.4)

The results of the estimated equation of the effects of FDI on human capital are given in Table 5. The coefficient of determination is 57% and it appears that FDI inflows have no influence on the rate of education in the CEMAC. This result does not include that of Blomström and Kokko (2003) which emphasise the relative importance of NMFs on higher education in the host countries.

The non significance of the effects of FDI on human capital in CEMAC may be due to the proxy variable chosen as human capital. On the other hand, the increase in domestic investment, per capita income and employment encourage young education.

Table 5: Estimation of the human capital equation

Dependent variable:HC				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	-408.707	216.633	-1.886	0.060
HC(-1)	0.457	0.177	2.582(***)	0.010
EMP	0.226	0.227	0.995	0.320
FDI	-3.119	2.719	-1.146	0.252
GR	3.055	2.612	1.169	0.243
IC	5.895	2.680	2.198(**)	0.017
INV	10.354	4.879	2.122(**)	0.028
IMP	5.274	10.631	0.496	0.620
IFR	-0.032	0.096	-0.341	0.733
EXR	20.873	14.838	1.406(*)	0.160
R squared	0.579	Mean dependent var		19.998
Adjusted R squared	0.461	S.D.dependent var		1.918
S.E. of regression	1.407	Sum squared resid		63.381
Durbin Waston stat	2.075			

Student test in parenthesis: (***) significant at 1%, (**) significant at 5%.

P-value: relative to the test performed. Robust test for autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity.

4.1.5. The effects of FDI on per capita income (LnIC, eq. 5)

The model results presented in Table 6 give a coefficient of determination of 94% and an adjusted coefficient of determination of 93%. The effects of FDI are significant with a probability of 10%. A change

in FDI leads to an increase in per capita income in the same direction. The result obtained here shows that the behaviour of FDI can play a certain role on the standard of living in CEMAC countries. Indeed, the recovery in oil and other commodity prices, Combined with the new discoveries in the oil fields, FDI flows have been revived over the past decade and the level of income per capita has doubled or even tripled in some countries in the area. Imports of capital goods and human capital are also significant and have an impact on per capita income. In other words, the more a country has the opportunity to import capital goods and devote more resources to its education, the more income per capita can increase.

Table 6: Estimation of the national income per capita equation

Dependent variable:IC				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	-11.74	9.620	-1.221	0.223
IC(-1)	0.621	0.137	4.504(***)	0.000
EMP	1.645	1.754	0.937	0.349
FDI	0.218	0.132	1.642(**)	0.097
GR	0.001	0.169	0.008	0.993
HC	0.031	0.012	2.599(***)	0.0009
INV	-0.040	0.298	-0.135	0.892
IMP	1.040	0.458	2.267(**)	0.024
IFR	-0.004	0.004	-0.975	0.330
EXR	0.608	0.595	1.020	0.308
R squared	0.945	Mean dependent var		3.145
Adjusted R squared	0.930	S.D.dependent var		0.384
S.E. of regression	0.101	Sum squared resid		0.327
Durbin Waston stat	1.701			

Student test in parenthesis: (***) significant at 1% and (**) significant at 5%. P-value: relative to the test performed.

4.1.6. The effects of FDI on domestic investment (In INV, eq.6)

The econometric estimate of equation 6 is given in Table 7. The coefficient of determination is 57% and the adjusted coefficient of determination is 46%. The effects of FDI on domestic investment are significant with a negative sign. A change in FDI results in a change in domestic investment in the opposite direction. One can therefore apparently retain the existence of a «crowding out» phenomenon between FDI and domestic investments in CEMAC. This situation seems to have several explanations: (i) The restructuring of the economy of the CEMAC countries under structural adjustment and particularly in Cameroon, the leading country, has led to the liquidation of para-public enterprises, which were acquired by subsidiaries of foreign firms. Local firms had neither the financial means nor the

human capital to compete with FMN subsidiaries during the liquidation of state-owned enterprises. The FMN prefer to buy at low prices from existing companies and restructure them rather than create new ones.

Over the past twenty years, it is estimated that Cameroon has sold more than 250 public and para-public companies to foreign investors. Even companies in the strategic sectors dear to Stiglitz such as water were sold to the subsidiaries of the American and French MFNs for the most part.

Table 7: Estimation of the domestic investment equation

Dependent variable:INV				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	-13.83	15.84	-0.873	0.383
IC	0.379	0.256	1.478(*)	0.000
EMP	1.777	2.675	0.664	0.506
FDI	-0.583	0.194	-3.002(***)	0.002
GR	0.088	0.188	0.470	0.638
HC	-0.008	0.021	-0.420	0.674
INV(-1)	0.266	0.161	1.654(*)	0.092
IMP	2.722	0.752	3.616(**)	0.0007
IFR	0.013	0.007	1.909(**)	0.057
EXR	1.182	0.959	1.232	0.218
INF	0.029	0.027	1.090	0.276
INT	-0.0001	0.001	-0.282	0.777
R squared	0.573	Mean dependent var		7.575
Adjusted R squared	0.460	S.D.dependent var		0.102
S.E. of regression	0.398	Sum squared resid		2.612
Durbin Waston stat	1.697			

Student test in parenthesis: (***) significant at 1% and (**) significant at 5%. P-value: relative to the test performed.

4.1.7. Effects of FDI on infrastructure (LnIFR, equation 7)

The results presented in Table 8 show a coefficient of determination of 90% and an adjusted coefficient of determination of 87%. The effects of FDI on infrastructures are significant at the 5% threshold with a Student test of 2.11. We also see that exports, per capita income and employment have a direct impact on infrastructure. This result is very noticeable at the moment in CEMAC where the mobile phone boom breaks the distances formerly maintained by the glaring lack of road and maritime infrastructure. In general, the exploitation of oil resources has facilitated the creation of road, hospital and educational infrastructure in order to make livable the villages in which expatriate workers reside. Everywhere, small towns with modern infrastructure in the fields of water, electricity, construction and sports have been

built on oil sites. Cities like Limbe in Cameroon, Ndoba in Chad and Port-gentil in Libreville have become heads of departments thanks to oil exploitation.

Table 8: Estimating the Infrastructure Equation

Dependent variable:IFR				
Number of observations:377				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Constant	-148.227	54.73	-2.708	0.007
IC	1.25	0.904	1.387(*)	0.066
EMP	27.632	9.816	2.815(***)	0.0005
FDI	1.261	0.595	2.116(**)	0.035
GR	0.946	1.006	0.940	0.347
HC	0.0309	0.071	0.433	0.665
INV	3.134	1.647	1.902(**)	0.058
IMP	1.495	1.480	-1.009	0.313
IFR(-1)	0.053	0.166	3.19(***)	0.001
EXP	7.871	3.369	2.33	0.020
R squared	0.90	Mean dependent var		39.735
Adjusted R squared	0.87	S.D.dependent var		15.952
S.E. of regression	5.64	Sum squared resid		1020.43
Durbin Waston stat	1.80			

Student test in parenthesis: (***) significant at 1%, (**) significant at 5%. P-value: relative to the test performed.

4.2. The effects of FDI on potential growth factors

The analysis of equations 1 to 7 suggests that, in general, FDI inflows into CEMAC tend directly to favour exports, infrastructure, per capita income, employment, imports of capital goods and indirectly, human capital through national per capita income. In addition, it is necessary to mention the additional effects of FDI through different amplification loops on infrastructure (IFR) and domestic investment (INV) via exports (EXP) or employment (EMP) and the effects of FDI on human capital (HC) through national income per capita (IC), or on domestic investment (INV) and human capital through imports of capital goods (IMP) and per capita income.

Finally, through the different interrelated relationships estimated (i) between infrastructure (IFR) and domestic investment (INV), (ii) between capital goods imports (IMP) and per capita income (IC), (iii) between per capita income and human capital (HC), it appears that FDI plays a significant role in all the potential factors of growth considered.

- Moreover, FDI hurts domestic investment, a crowding out effect on local businesses. This negative effect of FDI on domestic investment indirectly affects human capital, income, infrastructure, and employment.

Student test in parenthesis: (**) significant at 5%, P-value relative to the test performed

5. Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that given our estimates and simulations, the effects of FDI on growth in CEMAC are largely positive. The effects of FDI in a country depend not only on its economic performance measured by the rate of growth but also on its economic weight, its level of infrastructure, and the articulation of economic sectors. In addition, one may wonder if some endogenous growth is possible beyond FDI for some CEMAC States. This reflection deserves to be deepened because as we know, the good performance of the growth of the CEMAC before the FDI boom was facilitated by a good performance of the terms of trade, and especially because there were no producers south-for certain tropical products.

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